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Resolution of Neck, Mid-Back, and Abdominal Pain and Spontaneous Lung Collapse in a 4-Year-Old Female Following Correction of Cervical Lordosis Using Chiropractic BioPhysics® Spinal Rehabilitation: A Case Report and 22-Month Follow-up.

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Abstract

Objectives: To demonstrate a case of resolution of spontaneous lung collapse in a 4-year-old female patient following Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®) structural spinal rehabilitation.

Clinical Features: A 4-year-old female presented with her mother to a corrective chiropractic clinic with neck (NP) and mid-back pain (MBP). The patient's mother reported a history of various health problems, including asthma, spontaneous pneumothorax/collapsed lung, and abdominal pain and bloating, which were being medically managed with no success. The mother reported that the patient had been to the hospital several times, but with no answers or solutions. The mom stated that the patient had been born prematurely and was experiencing difficulty sleeping, loss of concentration, nervousness, and irritability. The patient stated that the MBP came on gradually and became so severe that it prohibited any activity occurring 76-100% of the time. The lung collapse in the lower left lobe and middle right lobe was spontaneous, and the pediatric pulmonologist provided no specific cause and speculated that the patient is immunodeficient and recommended isolation from other children. The patient's mother reported that the doctors prescribed the patient steroids, inhalers, and antibiotics. The patient reported the NP as dull, achy, and spasmodic and came on gradually and progressed to moderate intensity and limited activities of daily living (ADL) occurring 50-80% of the time. The patient reported the abdominal pain came on gradually and progressed to moderate intensity and limited activities of daily living (ADL) occurring 50-80% of the time. The patient reported pre-treatment visual analog scale (VAS) for MBP at 9/10, NP at 5/10, and the abdominal pain at 5/10 on a scale of 0-10 where 0=no pain and 10=max pain.

Pre-treatment posture analysis was performed using PostureScreen® Mobile Posture Analysis (PostureCo, Inc., Trinity, FL, USA) showing anterior head translation (+TzH), elevated right shoulder, and pelvic unleveling. Pre-treatment

neutral lateral cervical (NLC) radiographic examination analysis was performed using PostureRay® X-Ray Electronic Health Records Software (PostureCo, Inc., Trinity, FL, USA). Pre-treatment NLC radiograph showed cervical curvature (ARA C2-C7) measuring -9.3° (ideal is $30.6^\circ/27.8^\circ$) and second order buckling of the cervical spine with C2-C5 kyphosis.

Interventions & Outcomes: The patient received 21 in-office treatment sessions over 16.0 weeks including Diversified chiropractic spinal manipulation and CBP® Mirror Image® (MI) corrective chiropractic adjustments, therapeutic exercises, and cervical Denneroll™ extension traction. MI therapies involve positioning the patient in a corrected or over-corrected postural position. MI Adjustments involved positioning the patient head extension prone posture on a drop table to and applying adjustment manually, with drop table and with an Impulse® Adjusting Instrument (Neuromechanical Innovations, Chandler, AZ, USA).

Post-treatment NLC radiographs showed improvement in ARA C2-C7 to -20.9° with no buckling and correction of the cervical kyphosis. The patient's mother reported she had 0 incidences of spontaneous lung collapse since initiating care and that NP, MBP, and abdominal pain had resolved.

At long-term follow-up, approximately 22 months after post-treatment radiographs, the mother reported 0 incidences of spontaneous lung collapse, continued resolution of NP, MBP, and abdominal pain and was going to enroll the patient in public school. Long-term Follow-up NLC radiographs showed preserved improvement in ARA C2-C7.

Conclusion: The case shows resolution of spontaneous lung collapse in a 4-year-old female following correction of cervical lordosis using CBP® spinal rehabilitation. More research is needed investigating the somato-visceral effects of abnormal changes in spinal alignment and the impacts on spontaneous lung collapse.

Figure 1A-B. Pre-Treatment and Post-Treatment Neutral Lateral Cervical Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal cervical spinal alignment. The red lines represent the actual C2-T2 posterior tangent lines of the patient.

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Reduction of Back Pain Following Long-Term Correction of Thoracic Posture and Hyperkyphosis in a 15-Year-Old Male with Scheuermann's Kyphosis Using Chiropractic BioPhysics®: A Case Study and 2-Year Follow-Up.

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Abstract

Objective: To present a case of improvement in mid- (MBP) and low back pain (LBP) following long-term correction of thoracic posture and hyperkyphosis in a 15-year-old male with Scheuermann's kyphosis using Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®) Mirror Image® spinal rehabilitation protocols with a 2-year follow-up exam.

Clinical Features: A 15-year-old male presented with daily MBP and LBP. Pain was exacerbated by lifting, pushing, and other activities such as mowing the lawn. He reported that after a morning of work, he often needed to lie down for the rest of the day to relieve his pain. The patient also reported enduring social criticism/teasing at school regarding his hunchback posture.

The patient described his MBP and LBP as frequent (51–75% of the day) that he rated 3/10 on average and 8/10 at worst on a numeric rating scale (NRS) of 0-10 where 0=no pain and 10=max pain. Pre-treatment lateral thoracolumbar radiographs showed increased thoracic kyphosis (ARA T1-T12) measuring 70.1° (ideal is 44°) and posterior thoracic translation (Tz T12-S1) measuring -83.0 mm (ideal is 0 mm) (Figure 1A).

Intervention and Outcomes: The patient underwent 80 in-office CBP® treatments over 8 months. Treatment included CBP® Mirror Image® (MI) adjustments using a drop table in the corrective posture (i.e. thoracic cage translated anterior to the pelvis) and Diversified spinal manipulation applied to the thoracic and lumbar spine. MI spinal exercises performed against a wall with a 4-inch trapezoidal block at the apex of the thoracic kyphosis. The patient was instructed to lift the sternum and draw it posteriorly while maintaining pelvic contact with the wall thereby inducing both anterior thoracic translation and thoracic extension. Exercises were performed for 8 minutes prior to traction. MI spinal traction was performed supine using the 3-D Denneroll™ Traction Table System (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia). Thoracic Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotic (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) served as a fulcrum for thoracic extension and was placed on a 4-inch block at the apex of the thoracic kyphosis (T8). Two straps applied anterior-to-posterior (A-P) tension above and below the apex. Traction started at 6 minutes and increased by 2 minutes per visit until reaching 20 minutes. When 20 minutes was reached, straps were tightened midway through each session to increase extension force. The patient was also instructed to use a Thoracic Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotic at home daily for 15–20 minutes. He reported using it with varying consistency between 3-4 times per week during the course of care.

Post-treatment MBP and LBP NRS revealed improvements in pain levels to 2/10 on average and 5/10 at worst with a reduced frequency to intermittent (26–50% of the day). The patient reported less need for rest after physical exertion. Post-treatment lateral thoracolumbar radiographs showed improvements in ARA T1-T12 to 63.7° and Tz T12-S1 to -40.0 mm (Figure 1B).

The patient reported no professional treatment for back pain in the 2 years following the post-treatment exam. A 2-year follow-up exam revealed further improvement in pain frequency to 1-2 times per month following intense activity. The patient states he is able to lift weights and play golf without pain. He stated that he performed his home prescribed traction

only when he became symptomatic. 2-year follow-up radiographs show maintained improvement in ARA T1-T12 at 63.7° and further improvement in Tz T12-S to -22.0 mm (Figure 1C). The patient also reported increased self-confidence and reduced teasing at school.

Conclusion: This case demonstrates that CBP® Mirror Image® spinal rehabilitation protocols can be effective in reducing thoracic hyperkyphosis and posterior thoracic translation in a patient with Scheuermann's kyphosis which may be associated with pain, function, disability, and social criticism/teasing. Improvements in spinal alignment and posture, pain, and function were maintained for 2 years, indicating that CBP® may be an effective treatment for thoracic hyperkyphosis and abnormal posture yielding long-term results.

Figure 1A-C. A) Pre-Treatment, B) Post-Treatment, and C) 2-Year Long-Term Follow-Up Lateral Thoracolumbar Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal thoracic and lumbar spinal alignment. The red lines represent the actual T1-L5 posterior tangent lines of the patient. The yellow dotted lines represent the sagittal vertical axis (SVA) from the posterior, inferior aspect of S1. The yellow solid lines represent the sagittal translation distance from the posterior, inferior aspect of T12 with respect to the SVA from the posterior, inferior aspect of S1.

3

Successful Treatment of a 38-Year-Old Female with Headaches and Chronic Neck and Low Back Pain and Disability Following Correction of Abnormal Cervical and Thoracic Spinal Alignment and Posture Using Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®): A Case Study and 3-Month Follow-Up.

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Abstract

Objective: To present the successful structural correction of cervical lordosis and thoracic kyphosis in a patient with cervicogenic headache (HA), chronic neck pain (cNP), and chronic low back pain (cLBP), complicated by scoliosis and obesity. This case also highlights associated improvements in pain, disability, daily function, and health-related quality of life (HRQOL) following non-surgical treatment using Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®).

Clinical Features: A 38-year-old female presented with daily HAs, cNP, cLBP, and difficulty with activities of daily living (ADL) such as prolonged sitting and grocery shopping. Her symptoms limited productivity at work, which involved extended hours of computer use and paperwork. Her initial body mass index (BMI) was 39.1. She had undergone years of traditional chiropractic care and suboccipital injections without lasting relief. Her goals included improved sitting tolerance, greater independence with daily tasks, and reduced reliance on over-the-counter (OTC) pain medications.

Pre-treatment radiographic analysis revealed cervical kyphosis with a cervical curvature (ARA C2–C7) measuring 11.3° (ideal is -42°) and anterior head translation (TzH C2-C7) measuring 31.4 mm (ideal is 0 mm) (Figure 1A); thoracic hyperkyphosis with ARA T1–T12 measuring 68.5° (ideal is 44°) (Figure 2A); and thoracic dextroscoliosis with a Cobb angle T5-T11 (T7 apex) measuring 13.9° (ideal is 0°) (Figure 3A). Pre-treatment patient-reported outcome measures (PROM) were preformed. Numeric rating scale (NRS) for LBP was 5/10 on average and 7/10 at worst and for NP and HA was 3/10 on average and 6/10 at worst on a scale of 0-10 where 0=no pain and 10=max pain. Neck disability index (NDI) was 26% (mild disability due to NP) and Revised Oswestry Disability Index for LBP (RODI) was 30% (moderate disability due to LBP). Short Form 36-item questionnaire (SF-36) revealed Physical Functioning (PF) at 65/100, Energy/Fatigue (E/F) at 35/100, and Emotional Well-Being (EWB) at 72/100.

Intervention and Outcome: A six-month CBP® structural spinal rehabilitation protocol was implemented, including Mirror Image® (MI) postural exercises, spinal traction using the Universal Tractioning Systems (UTS) Total Spine unit (Universal Tractioning Systems, Inc., Las Vegas, NV, USA), and Diversified spinal manipulative therapy (SMT). Treatment was delivered three times per week for the first three months and once weekly for the following three months (Figure 4A-B).

Post-treatment radiographs revealed improvements in TzH C2-C7 to 5.6 mm and ARA C2–C7 to -25.6° (Figure 1B), ARA T1–T12 to 52.6° (Figure 2B), and Cobb T5-T11 (T7) to 10.2° (Figure 3B). Post-treatment PROMs revealed improvements in NRS for LBP to 3/10 on average and 6/10 at worst and for NP and HA to 3/10 on average and 6/10 at worst, NDI to 20% (mild disability due to NP) and RODI to 16% (mild disability due to LBP), and SF-36 PF to 80/100, E/F to 40/100, and EWB to 80/100. The patient reported increased sitting and working tolerance and the ability to complete errands without discomfort. The patient reduced her reliance on OTC pain medications and reported meaningful weight loss during care.

Conclusion: This case demonstrates that structural spinal rehabilitation using the CBP® technique can lead to significant improvements in cervical lordosis and forward head posture, thoracic kyphosis, and thoracic scoliosis curvature in a patient with cNP, cervicogenic HA, and cLBP. These corrections were accompanied by reductions in pain and disability and improvements in functional capacity and HRQOL. This case supports the clinical utility of non-surgical structural correction in the management of complex spinal deformities and chronic musculoskeletal pain and dysfunction. Further research is warranted to assess the long-term efficacy and generalizability of these outcomes in broader patient populations.

Figure 1A-B. Pre-Treatment and Post-Treatment Neutral Lateral Cervical Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal cervical spinal alignment. The red lines represent the actual C2-C7 posterior tangent lines of the patient.

Figure 2A-B. Pre-Treatment and Post-Treatment Lateral Thoracic Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal thoracic spinal alignment. The red lines represent the actual T1-T12 posterior tangent lines of the patient.

Figure 3A-B. Pre-Treatment and Post-Treatment Anteroposterior Thoracic Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal coronal thoracic spinal alignment. The red lines represent the actual T1-T12 spinal alignment of the patient. The yellow lines represent the Cobb measurement for T5-T11 (T7 Apex).

Figure 4A-B. CBP® Mirror Image® Corrective
A) Spinal Exercises, and B) Mechanical Traction

Image Features: The red arrows indicate movement or force applied to the body during MI therapies.

4

Resolving Chronic Neck Pain and Disability Following Correction of Cervical Lordosis and Posture Using Chiropractic BioPhysics® Structural Spinal Rehabilitation: A Case Series of 10 Patients. [Oral Presentation at CBP® 45th Annual Convention, September 15-17, 2023, Grapevine, TX, USA]

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Abstract

Objective: The purpose of this case series is to demonstrate the alleviation of persistent neck pain and disability following correction of sagittal cervical spinal alignment and posture using Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®) structural spinal rehabilitation in 10 patients.

Clinical Features: Ten adults (2 females and 8 males) with a mean age of 41.9 ± 13.5 years (age range 28-75 years), mean height of 175.7 ± 0.5 cm, and mean weight of 75.3 ± 5.9 kg presented to a structural spinal rehabilitation chiropractic clinic with persistent neck pain lasting greater than 3 months

Inclusion criteria for patient selection for this case series was the presence of neck pain (NP) lasting greater than 3 months, pain disability index (PDI) score exceeding 20/70, and pre- and post-treatment neutral lateral cervical (NLC) radiographs.

Pre-treatment patient-reported outcome measures (PROM) were performed. Mean initial numeric rating scale (NRS) was 6.8 ± 1.8 on a scale of 0-10 where 0=no pain and 10=max pain, indicating moderate pain, and a mean PDI score of 32.8 ± 16.8 on a scale of 0-70 where 0=no disability due to pain and 10=maximum disability due to pain, indicating severe-to-extreme disability due to NP (Table 1). Initial radiographic analysis revealed mean anterior head translation (TzH C2-C7) measuring 27.6 ± 17.0 mm (ideal is 0 mm) and cervical curvature (ARA C2-C7) measuring $-21.2^\circ \pm 9.2^\circ$ (ideal is -42°) (Table 1, Figure 1-2A).

Intervention & Outcome: The participants underwent two rounds of corrective care in the CBP method, each involving 36 visits, making a total of 72 in-office sessions. These sessions incorporated CBP® Mirror Image® (MI) chiropractic spinal adjustments, spinal exercises, and corrective spinal traction. MI adjustments were conducted by extending the neck (-RxH) and utilizing a posterior head translation (-TzH) in order to improve the decreased cervical curvature and the anterior head translation. MI corrective spinal traction and exercises were utilized to create long-term correction of cervical spinal alignment and posture.

Post-treatment patient-reported outcome measures (PROM) were performed. There were improvements in mean initial NRS to 0.9 ± 1.4 , indicating mild pain, and a mean PDI score to 3.6 ± 2.2 , indicating no-to-mild disability due to NP (Table 1). These improvements indicate significant reduction or resolution of disability associated with NP. Post-Treatment radiographic analysis revealed improvement in mean TzH C2-C7 to 13.8 ± 8.8 mm and ARA C2-C7 to $-29.5^\circ \pm 7.2^\circ$ (Table 1, Figure 1-2B).

Conclusions: This series of 10 cases underscores the capacity of CBP® corrective chiropractic care to alleviate chronic NP of three months or more associated with a PDI of 20 or greater. This study shows that CBP® structural spinal chiropractic holds

promise for patients with chronic NP and disability who have previously encountered ineffective rehabilitation interventions that did not emphasize spinal alignment and posture. Further investigations are needed to explore the potential implications of CBP® in this specific context.

Table 1. Pre- and Post-Treatment Neutral Lateral Cervical Radiograph and Patient-Reported Outcome Measures

Patient	Neutral Lateral Cervical Radiograph				Patient Reported Outcome Measures			
	Pre-Treatment ARA C2-C7 (°)	Post-Treatment ARA C2-C7 (°)	Pre-Treatment TzH C2-C7 (mm)	Post-Treatment TzH C2-C7 (mm)	Pre-Treatment NRS	Post-Treatment NRS	Pre-Treatment PDI	Post-Treatment PDI
1	-32.0	-40.0	52.7	14.1	38	0	8	0
2	-10.0	-28.0	39.2	18.6	40	3	8	0
3	-26.0	-39.0	2.6	0.0	31	3	4	0
4	-5.0	-25.2	23.7	17.7	32	2	5	0
5	-9.5	-28.3	13.1	5.9	40	5	8	1
6	-23.4	-28.5	48.3	25.0	26	3	5	2
7	-19.0	-27.6	25.3	24.3	31	4	9	0
8	-17.5	-16.6	18.4	19.4	24	8	8	4
9	-27.5	-24.1	13.1	5.9	28	4	5	0
10	-41.6	-37.3	39.4	6.9	38	4	8	2
Mean	-21.2	-29.5	27.6	13.8	32.8	3.6	6.8	0.9
STD	9.2	7.2	17.0	8.8	5.9	2.2	1.9	1.4

Figure 1A-B. Pre- and Post-Treatment Neutral Lateral Cervical Radiographs (Patient 1)

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal cervical spinal alignment. The red lines represent the actual C2-C7 posterior tangent lines of the patient. The yellow lines represent craniocervical measurements (e.g. Chamberlain’s line and the atlas plane line).

Figure 2A-B. Pre- and Post-Treatment Neutral Lateral Cervical Radiographs (Patient 2)

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal cervical spinal alignment. The red lines represent the actual C2-C7 posterior tangent lines of the patient. The yellow lines represent craniocervical measurements (e.g. Chamberlain’s line and the atlas plane line).